

Effect of Population Growth on Urban Expansion in Peri-urban Areas: The case of Oyi Local Government Area, Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract

An increase in the number of persons in a particular settlement leads to a corresponding increase in the demand for housing and infrastructure. In Oyi LGA, the population is increasing and there is a corresponding demand for housing resulting in the outward growth of the city into the suburbs. This paper therefore examined the level to which urban expansion in Oyi LGA is predicted by population growth. Data for the study were obtained using copies of questionnaires, consultations, and remote sensing techniques. Data were further analysed using simple percentages and multiple regression analysis based on Statistical Package for Social Sciences. The result of the analysis showed that population growth in the study area largely predicts urban expansion in the study area. This implies that urban expansion is influenced by the growth of population in the study area. Being that population growth triggers land use changes through urban expansion, there is a need to negotiate strategies that will help maintain the optimum population in the study area. Equally, environmental protection strategies should be upheld.

Keywords: Housing, Population, urban expansion, Nkwelle Ezunaka and Ogbunike

1. Introduction

Globally, the upsurge in human population, which is largely tied to economic, social, and physical changes is linked to rapid urbanization and industrialization. These factors give rise to intense pressure on agricultural resources, through uncontrolled encroachment into farmlands (Eliud, Lucy, Bernard & Samuel, 2019). However, urbanization and population growth are bound to increase in the next three decades, with not less than two third of the world population residing in urban centres by the year 2050 (Assem, Maria, August, & Carl-Johan, 2019). This is in accordance with World Bank (2000) forecast which suggests that there would be an unprecedented growth in global population with not less than seventy percent (70%) of the world population living in towns and cities (Drebold, 2017). There statistics show

that most peri-urban areas will later become urban areas due to growth and city expansion and food production is likely to experience decline.

Nigeria has been identified as the fastest urbanizing country in sub-Saharan African with an annual growth rate of 3% and the, most of the growth is recorded in cities such as Lagos, Abuja, Markurdi, Kano, (Lorliam and Ortserga, 2019). Urban sprawling, as well as environmental change, has to a large extent transformed the image and complexity of food system in urban and peri-urban areas, where food security and supply is of utmost importance (Assem, Maria, August, and Carl-Johan, 2019). It should be noted that increasing population has negative implications on the pattern of land use especially for agricultural, residential and commercial uses (Wapwera, Jiriko & Mallo, 2015). For instance, current projections have shown that the population of the study area has increased from 168,201 persons in 2009 (FRN, 2009) to 233,799 persons in 2021. By 2030, it is estimated that 299,263 persons will be residing in the study area. While there is agricultural land decline, food security is threatened because the production of food is carried out on the land, and land is a major factor of production. In fact, land is rated first in the factors of production. Therefore, urban expansion which manifests in the turning of agricultural land to built-up areas has negative implications on food security. Specifically, a pilot survey within the study area has shown a decline in agricultural land over time. The main drivers of urban expansion in the study area are the sprawling of the city of Onitsha town and its environs. However, Onitsha town is a major urban setting in Southeast Nigeria and it attract people from different regions in Nigeria. The continuous demand for land for housing development and other uses without a corresponding area of availability of land within Onitsha town make developers to seek for alternative areas of land resulting in demand for land for housing development in the study area.

Another reason that favours housing development, sprawling and urban expansion in the study area is the fact that Onitsha town is located within considerable distance such that commuters can drive within a short distance of about 15minutes to the town located in the suburb. House rent in the study area is relatively affordable compared to the cost of accommodation in Onitsha town. Notably, cost of land tends to be considerably cheaper and even more, available in the study area than in Onitsha town hence, demand for agricultural land has been a recurring decimal over time in the study area. From the foregoing the study area tends to be on the receiving end of population growth and urban expansion/sprawling without adequate attempts by researchers to appraise the extent to which such agricultural land decline affects food security.

Available studies (Obialor, Alozie, Oti and Peter, 2019; Ayadiuno, Ndulue and Mozie, 2022) appear concerned about the level to which population growth affect urban areas neglecting, the suburbs which have long been captured by developers looking to set housing structures and other developments. Further, studies have not been able to appraise the extent to which food security is being threatened using remote sensing and GIS techniques. Besides, the concepts of public health and sustainable development have not been applied in the analysis of urban expansion and food security with reference to the study area. From the above, it is clear that there is inadequate knowledge on the extent to which continuous urban expansion can trigger food scarcity especially due to population growth. Equally, there is inadequate knowledge relating to the application of change detection techniques, remote sensing and GIS technologies in mapping out land use/land cover change in the study area. Based on these observations and the need to contribute maximally to knowledge while making policy statements that will be useful in stemming the tide of unplanned urban expansion in the study area, hence, this study was conceived.

2. Global Population Increase

Globally, it has been estimated that 83 million people is being added to the world population every year. The increase in population is expected to increase (UN, 2017). Similarly, Africa continues to record high rates of population growth, the population of 26 African countries is expected to double their present size between the year 2017 and 2050 (UN, 2017). Environmental sustainability as well as sustainable food protection in Africa is under intense pressure, due to rapid population growth. This trend according to Anah (2009) is linked to the rate of increase in poverty that is ravaging African countries, such as Cameroon, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Malawi, Niger, Nigeria, Uganda, Tanzania among others.

Global population growth is estimated to be 6.7 billion by the year 2007. Besides Asia, and Africa have been the world's second most populated continents since 2000 (14%). However, this is closely followed by Europe (11%), Latin America and the Caribbean (9%), North America (5%) and far behind, Oceania (1%) (OECD, 2007). In line with this, the United Nations estimates that approximately one in eight persons globally was undernourished by 2014, it has been documented that most of these people live in developing countries, where more than 14 percent of the people are unable to meet their dietary energy requirements. Progress has been made in southern Asia, northern Africa and most countries of eastern and south eastern Asia, as well as in Latin America. Consequently, feeding this growing global

population in the years to come will require producing more food and distributing it in a manner that reaches more people.

It is worthy to note that Nigeria is currently the 7th most populated country worldwide. According to Odey (2020), the unprecedented growth in human population in Nigeria is one of the reasons for environmental decay and poor developmental growth. Odey (2020) also noted that developing countries like Nigeria and some other countries in sub-Saharan region, are constrained in terms of effectively managing their ever-increasing populace.

Nigeria is considered the most populous country in Africa and the eighth most populous country in the world. With 182 million inhabitants in 2015, and over 200 million persons in 2021, Nigeria accounted for 5% of births globally (and one fifth of all births on the African continent), but by 2050 it is projected that one in every ten children worldwide will be born in Nigeria. In the last five decades, Nigeria's population has been on the increase due to factors such as increase in birth rates. It has been observed that growth was fastest in the 1980s after child mortality has reduced slightly.

However, a study on population growth and distribution in Nigeria, showed that population growth in Nigeria is influenced by birth, death and migration (Ebele, 2009). Ebele (2009) further observed that Nigerian population growth was triggered by oil boom and subsequent expansion of economic activities from the mid-seventies; hence, the growth rate in Nigeria has been on the increase with an average growth rate of 3.20%.

Population Growth/Urban Expansion and Agricultural land Decline

Population increase/urban expansion manifests in the decline of agricultural land as noted in existing studies. For instance, in Asia urban expansion poses diverse economic and environmental challenges to agricultural land bringing about decline. Kaifang *et al.* (2016) noted that food shortage/scarcity is attributed to uncontrolled urban expansion which is the aftermath of a decline in the land dedicated to agricultural development and food production. It was outlined that between the year 2001 and 2013, urban areas in China increased from 31,076 km² in 2001 to 80,887km² in 2013, which implies a setback in food production due to the unprecedented growth in urban space which encroach into over 33,080km² of its valuable agricultural land.

Helge (2017) noted that the industrialization of Hanoi has impacted on the city food security. There is an adverse increase in the demand for agricultural product, being made

possible through the decrease in the present agricultural land from 75 percent in 1993 to less than 50 percent presently (Helge , 2017).The conversion of agriculture lands to residential and industrial uses is common in urbanized cities. For instance, in a Chilean city of about 500,000 inhabitants, it was observed that 1,734 hectares of wetland and 1,975 hectares of agricultural land and forest were converted to residential landuse over a period of 1975 to 2000.

In addition, Chinese urbanization is more likely to worsen its food security, as discovered by Li and Jiang (2013) study on the impact of urban expansion on agricultural resources in China. The findings showed a negative correlation between urbanization and agricultural land use intensity. It is critical to know the possibility of Chinas urban growth, agricultural land use and how food production can be made more sustainable. Meanwhile, Ademiluyi, Okude and Akanni (2008) opined that a change in land cover is a global trend that was mainly triggered by factors such as urbanization, industrialization as well as large-scale agricultural production. More so, this phenomenon has been observed to be worse in Africa due to the high rate of deforestation and the complete reliance on primary resources (Adepoju and Adepoju, 2016).

These findings were similar to the views of Satterthwaite, Gordon, and Cecilia, (2010), on urbanization and its implications for food and farming. It was observed that urbanization hurts agriculture. For instance, the loss of agricultural land to urban expansion and an urban bias in public funding for infrastructures, services, and subsidies were attributed to urbanization. The economic and urbanization factors are the major reasons for uncontrolled land use change. In India, within its environment built-up areas are increasing drastically from 2,611 hectares as observed in 2011 to 5,36 hectares in 2018. This increase over a period of seven years has taken over agricultural land and plantations in Aligarh city thereby threatening food sustainability (Sadaf and Himanchal, 2019). In Accra, up to 2600 hectares of agricultural land is converted yearly due to urban expansion and the need for infrastructure and residential development in Ghana (Ira, 2009). These negative trends however imperil peri-urban agriculture thereby threatening food security.

Lorliam, and Ortserga (2019) observed that urban physical growth which is triggered by urbanization has the ability to create a negative return in the level of agricultural production in peri-urban areas of Markurdi, Nigeria. This trend is, however, due to the uncontrolled encroachment of urban physical growth on agricultural land use in peri-urban districts of Markurdi town. Their investigation lasted through the period of 1986 to 2016; satellite images and GIS techniques were adopted. It was discovered that existing built up areas had increased drastically from 8.73% in 1986 to 64.15% in the year 2016. Also, as compared to twenty (20) years ago, there was massive reduction in the size of farm lands. This setback implies an

increase in food insecurity and poor land use for both the urban poor and residents of peri-urban areas where this land use change is prevalent.

Moreover, a study carried out in Anambra State, Nigeria showed that the occurrence of food scarcity, disease, urban environmental challenges, and widespread hunger were attributed to unplanned urbanization and migration of people (Okoli, Okoro, & Adekitan, 2016). The reduction in agricultural land is an indication of urban expansion. This is however worsened in areas with little or no mechanism for effective monitoring of land use conversion from agricultural purposes to non-agricultural purposes, poor regulation and complete neglect of urban expansion have led to drastic consequences (Okoli et al., 2016).

Effects of population increase and urban expansion on food production/food security

Statistics between 2000 and 2002 by the Food and Agricultural Organization for 2000-2002 showed that 852 million people globally were undernourished. It is even worrisome to note that not less than 800 million people are still suffering from chronic undernutrition, hunger, and food insecurity in developing countries (FAO, 2004).

The United Nations estimated that about 805 million people, which is approximately one in eight, are undernourished (Fawole, Ilbasmis, and Ozkan, 2015). Fawole *et al.*, (2015) noted that the majority of these people are residing in developing countries where more than 14 percent of the people are unable to meet their dietary energy requirements. It is also worth noting that progress has been made in Southern Asia, Northern Africa and in Latin America. Food security and availability is highly threatened all over the world. Notably, in 2016 the number of undernourished was 815 million, as compared to 777 million people in 2015 and 900 million people in the year 2002. The significant increase is due to lack of international commitment to end hunger and guarantee food security by 2030 (FAO, 2017).

Given that Africa has the fastest rate of demographic growth in the world, the phenomenon has a long-term impact on the environment. where most of these problems manifest in forms such as drought that lead to starvation, degradation of soil quality and fragile ecosystem, leading to famine and a decline in food production (UNCTAD, 2018). John, Mark and Maximo (2012) emphasized the need for the use of investment in addressing global food insecurity and malnutrition pointing out that such market intervention must be focused on increasing rural incomes, while reducing hunger and poverty. The rationale for doing this is that there are approximately 925 million hungry people in the world.

Subsequently, the regional overview of food insecurity in Africa shows that sub-Saharan Africa recorded a significant decline in undernourished people from 33 percent to 23 percent between 1990-1992 and 2014-2016. Also, the total number of undernourished people tended to rise with an estimate of 220 million in 2014-2016 compared to 175.7 million in 1990-1992 (FAO, 2015). However, the number of undernourished people globally rose significantly in 2014 from 775 million people to 777 million in 2015. Sub-Saharan Africa is said to be highly affected with an alarming rate of 22.7 percent undernourished people in 2016. The situation in Eastern Africa was said to be very worrisome as up to one-third of the population is estimated to be undernourished (FAO, 2017)

According to the findings of Nwozor, Olanrewaju and Modupe (2019), food security is becoming a national priority in Nigeria, this is due to the fact that a vast majority of its 198.1 million population is food insecure. Agricultural activities in Nigeria have been impeded by national insecurity with a rise in the displacement of farmers and ancestral farming communities.

Otaha (2013) observed that the past four decades in Nigeria have witnessed a significant level of food insecurity which was triggered by the focus on the oil industry at the expense of intensified food production. Also, other factors that led to increased food shortages in Nigeria were the adoption of neo-liberal economic policies, such as devaluation of naira, as well as ethnic and religious conflicts, occurrence of flooding and drought in Nigeria (Otaha, 2013).

3. Methodology

Study Area

Oyi Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria. It lies between Latitudes 5⁰ and 7¹ North and Longitudes 6⁰ and 7¹ East. It has a land area of about 500square kilometres. The area experiences rainy season between April and October while the dry season spans between November to March annually. The area has a warm humid tropical climate, with an average rainfall of between 1520-2020mm per annum. Minimum and maximum temperatures range from 25°C to 30°C (Ifeka, and Akinbobola, 2015). The climate favours agricultural development. The residents of the area are largely involved in the production of oil palm, maize, rice, yam, cassava, and fishing activities. The five autonomous communities which make up Oyi LGA are Awkuzu, Nteje, Umunya, Ogbunike and Nkwelle-Ezunaka. The communities are known for their vast agricultural farming in both crop and livestock

production. Being agrarian in nature, they are essentially agric-based and reputed as one of the food baskets of Anambra State. It has wide arable land and the crops grown include: rice, yam seeds, cassava, cocoyam, maize and vegetables. Domestic animals are goats, sheep and fowl. Due to the system of land ownership in the area, cultivation of crop is relatively in small land holdings by individual farmers who practice cropping often with fallow system (Nkamigbo, Nwoye, Makwudo and Gbughemobi, 2019). Figures 1 shows the geographic location of the study area.

Figure 1: Locational Map of the Study Area

Source: Jorinno Survey Services & Assoc. Nig., (2021)

Methods

The study was carried out in Oyi LGA. Basically, two peri-urban areas were chosen. The areas are Nkwelle Ezunaka and Ogbunike areas. Data were obtained on the population and the level of urban expansion in the areas. Data were specifically collected from primary and secondary sources. Specifically, data were obtained using Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information System (GIS) technique, administration of questionnaire, interview and

observation of the trend in urban expansion in Nkwelle and Ogbunike in Oyi Local Government Area. Data were further obtained from the National Population Commission (NPC), Department of Agriculture and Rural Development in Anambra state, Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Lands, Physical Planning and Urban Development in Anambra state, Oyi Local Government, Local Planning Authorities. Other important sources include agencies, internet, journals, Gazettes, textbooks, lecture notes, etc. Information under this category serves as a guide in determining the population of the study area and data from review of literature. Based on the existing population, a total of 400 copies of questionnaire were administered. The sample was established using the Taro Yamane formular. The fomular for establishing the sample is shown as follows;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \quad \text{Equation (4.1)}$$

Where: n = Sample size, N= Population size, e = Level of Significance/ limit of error, 1= unity (constant).

Descriptive tools such as simple percentages, frequencies, means/averages, tables and pie charts were used in data presentation, summarization and interpretation. The two hypothesis that were formulated were tested using Multitple Linear Regression in Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

4. Discussions and Findings

Effect of population increase on Urban Expansiom

To achieve the objective, estimation of the Population Distribution of Nkwelle-Ezunaka and Ogbunike from High Resolution Remotely Sensed Imagery was adopted. Thus, using the total numbers of household units derived from remote sensing imageries this was achieved and the result was validated using statistical computation at 2.83% rate of population increase. Manual extraction of the built-up footprint was done in ArcGIS, that is, the 2016 Aerial Photograph boundaries of the two study areas that were obtained from Capital Territory Development Authority (ACTA). Figure 2 was digitized to create Building Layer Definition (BLD). BLD gives a detailed survey of number of buildings at the level of individual household units, schools and commercial area were classified; a high spatial resolution remotely sensed imagery was used to define the location of individual buildings. Apart from population estimation, this information can help to build a Central Business District (CBD) tax parcel data, urban parcels database, natural preserves database, and urban building database, among others

Figure 2: Multi-Spectral Aerial Photograph of Nkwelle-Ezunaka (2016)

Source: Awka Capital Territory Development Authority (ACTDA), 2018.

This work adopted the deterministic model for population estimation of the study area. Limited reconnaissance fieldwork was done before image digitization and immediately after the digitizing, ‘ground truthing’ follows to assist in providing information about the number of residents. The type of dwelling was collected, Ground control points were acquired with a Garmin 78s GPS, where other building statistics were obtained from GIS environment and the national Census data of 2006 was collected from NPC, Awka. Digital delineation of the houses within the study area was achieved through careful digitization of all the households and buildings in ArcGIS 10.5. Then, the total number of housing units was multiplied by the occupancy rate of housing units. The derived figure should be close to the total populations within both communities. All the buildings, especially, residential-building footprints was first delineated from the remote-sensing data using manual image digitizing process. Residential areas of the study sites were observed to be generally homogeneous in nature. Jean Bertoin (2016) noted that “The study of the dynamics of populations is a tool of fundamental importance, notably in Genetics, Ecology, and Epidemiology, to name just a few.

Thus, the estimated annual residential population figures of the area were produced statistically by projecting the official 2006 National Population of the two communities using their average annual growth rate. Because, 2006 was the last time census was officially conducted in Nigeria, for, other non-census years, mathematical models were used to estimate population changes from the census baseline, employing a range of data such as births, deaths, school enrollments, and building approvals. To evaluate population estimation accuracies, the projected population and results from physical analysis including field visitation and questionnaires were used. The results were compared to related population estimation studies from remote sensing techniques. This approach is unique, because many researchers don't usually have the patience to carry out manual digitizing of the building footprints but usually relied on ancillary GIS and remote sensing data for population estimation. Most studies estimated populations by land use areas or image pixel characteristics.

Figure 3. Projected population of Nkwelle-Ezunaka Districts

Figure 4. Projected population of Ogbunike Districts

Figure 3 and 4 are estimated population of Nkwelle-Ezunaka and Ogbunike Districts. The figures show an upward increase in population of the pre-urban areas.

Furthermore, the census targets to survey the amount of people living in residential buildings. Population estimation by buildings is consistent with census data that are used for population modeling. Buildings are also generally contained within man-made or natural zones of which populations need to be estimated. During the fieldwork, a structured questionnaire was used as a tool for making sure that the sampled size locations were visited. A trained surveyor first collected information about the number of people sleeping on a regular basis in the building, by asking the owner of the building. Total number of buildings that was digitized in a given area is multiplied by the average household size, (figure 5.). The estimate of the actual population of the given area was obtained. This was now possible because, the total number of households' units in an area may be estimated from remote sensing images through image digitizing or classification. Green (1956) proposed using individual households obtained from aerial photographs for population estimation, while Porter (1956) was the first to actualize this methodology. Using equation 4.2, the estimation of the population of Nkwelle Ezunaka and Ogbunike communities in Anambra State using total number household units derived from remote sensing imageries was achieved.

$$\text{Popf} = \text{TnBd} * \text{AvgHdSize} \quad \text{Equation (4.2)}$$

Where, Popf = Population Figure,

TnBd = Total number of building in a given area,

AvgHdSize = average household size.

When analyzing the Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents obtained through focus group discussion, personal interview and questionnaire, the researcher noted that the highest frequency of family size of 167 (42%) in these communities fall within the range 5-6 children excluding their parents. From this experience, the average household size of five persons per house hold was adopted in this population estimation.

Figure 5. Digitized Map of Nkwelle-Ezunaka showing the building footprints

Thus, the total population of Nkwelle-Ezunaka was estimated by multiplying the total number of household units by the total number of persons normally living in a residence using equation 4.2.

Figure 6. Vectorised Landuse and Landcover Map of Nkwelle-Ezunaka

Figure 6 shows the Vectorised Landuse and Landcover Map of Nkwelle-Ezunaka, which depict the level of anthropogenic activities in the area. Similarly figure 7 is shows only the Road network Map

of Nkwelle-Ezunaka with this one can easily visualize the level of human development within this community.

Table 1: Building Footprints of Nkwelle-Ezunaka Community

LANDUSE	BUILDING UNITS	AREA (SQM)	POPULATION FIGURE
Residential Area	11850	1,715,963	11850 x 5 =59,250
Commercial Area	748	157,699.9	748 x 1=748
Industrial Area	51	28,860.57	51 x 1=51
Educational Area	117	43,748.76	117 x 1=117
Total	12,766	1,946,272.23	60,166

Table 1 is the Building Footprints of Nkwelle-Ezunaka Community that was used in the calculation of population figure of this area. Therefore, the estimated population figure of Nkwelle-Ezunaka = 59,250+748+51+117=60,166. While, the statistical population computation and projection at 2.83% growth rate shows that the population of Nkwelle-Ezunaka Community is 68,113. Details are shown in Figure 7 is a column demonstration of projected population of Nkwelle-Ezunaka Districts.

Figure 7 is a column demonstration of projected population of Nkwelle-Ezunaka Districts

Figure 8: Road network Map of Nkwelle-Ezunaka

Similarly, Figure 9 of Ogbunike 10cm High Resolution Multi-Spectral Aerial Photograph (2016) was digitized to create Building Layer Definition (BLD). BLD gives a detailed survey of the number of buildings at the level of individual households' units, schools and commercial area was classified; a high spatial resolution remotely sensed imagery was used to define the location of individual buildings.

Figure 9: Ogbunike 10cm High Resolution Multi-Spectral Aerial Photograph (2016)

Source: Awka Capital Territory Development Authority (ACTA), 2018.

Figure 10: Digitized Map of Ogbunike showing the building footprints

Table 10 is the Building Footprints of Ogbunike Community that was used in the calculation of population figure of this area. The total population of Ogbunike community was estimated by multiplying the total number of households' units with the total number of persons normally living in a residence using equation 4.3. However, the commercial, industrial and educational areas were multiplied with at least one person bearing in mind that its only security personnel that usually sleep there at night.

$$\text{Popf} = \text{TnBd} * \text{AvgHdSize} \quad \text{Equation 4.3.}$$

Where, Popf = Population Figure,
TnBd = Total number of building in a given area,
AvgHd Size = average household size.

Table 2: Building Footprints of Ogbunike Community

LANDUSE	BUILDING UNITS	AREA	POPULATION FIGURE
Residential Area	4065	710,798.1	4065 x 5=20,325
Commercial Area	168	36,627.95	168 x 1 =168
Industrial Area	77	69,649.49	77 x 1 = 77
Total	4,310	817,075.54	20,570

Thus, the estimated population figure of Ogbunike = 20,325+168+77=20,570

The statistical population computation and projection at 2.83% rate shows that the population of Ogbunike Community is 57,536. Details is shown in Figure 11 is a column demonstration of projected population of Ogbunike Districts. Unlike, the result of Nkwelle-Ezunaka where the result of both remote sensing techniques and projected population is very much close, that of Ogbunike is very much different, these may be due to wrong previous census figures or lack of accurate boundary delineations.

Figure 11: The projected population of Ogbunike Districts

Figure 12: Vectorised Landuse and Landcover Map of Ogbunike community

Figure 12 shows the Vectorised Landuse and Landcover Map of Ogbunike Community which depicts the level of anthropogenic activities in the area. Similarly, Figure 13 shows only the Road network Map of Ogbunike Community easily visualizing the level of human development within the studied community.

Figure 13: Road network Map of Ogbunike Community

Table 3: Model Summary for hypothesis One

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.989 ^a	.977	.977	.558

a. Predictors: (Constant), POPGRW

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 3 shows the model summary for hypothesis one which states that population growth has no significant effect on urban expansion in peri-urban areas of Nkwelle-Ezunaka and Ogbunike in Oyi Local Government Area. From the table, it shows that the correlation coefficient as represented by R is .989 representing a 99% relationship between the variables, while the

coefficient of determination as represented by R Square is .977 meaning that population growth has a 98% significant effect on urban expansion in peri-urban areas of Nkwelle-Ezunaka and Ogbunike in Oyi Local Government Area.

Table 4: ANOVA summary Table for Hypothesis One

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5362.244	1	5362.244	17201.949	.000 ^b
	Residual	124.066	398	.312		
	Total	5486.310	399			

a. Dependent Variable: URBEXP

b. Predictors: (Constant), POPGRW

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 4 reveals the test of hypothesis proper using F Statistics with a significant level of 0.05. From the result, it shows that the F is 17201.949 and the p-value as represented by Sig is .000 which is less than the level of significance used ($P\text{-value} < 0.05$). Going by this, the null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis and it is stated thus; population growth has a statistically significant effect on urban expansion in peri-urban areas of Nkwelle-Ezunaka and Ogbunike in Oyi Local Government Area.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

It was revealed in the study that there has been population explosion over time in the study area. The explosion in population was occasioned by increase in birth rate and urbanization. Specifically, the area in the fringes offer residential needs to residents in adjoining urban areas such as Onitsha and its environs. The resultant effect is the continuous efforts by developers to convert agricultural land which was formally used for production of food. This to a large extent suggests that food security remains threatened given the fact that while population is sporadically increasing and further unfolding impact on urban development, the agricultural lands are fast becoming converted hence. Food security, urban expansion and population growth become complex. The complexities are explained on the continuous

attempts by development to satisfy housing needs to ensure urban development/expansion without corresponding attempts to ensure land availability for food production which should bring about sustainability.

The study also explained that the population in the study area has been growing sporadically. Using the deterministic model for population estimation, and surveys projections were carried out. Equally, GIS technologies were applied in understanding the pattern and distribution of the population of residents across the study area. In all, it was observed that the number of persons in the area has increased over the years using 2006 census as the base year. Projections showed over 42 percent increase of the entire population. The household averages were noted to be predominantly 6 persons. The study area is therefore growing due to availability of infrastructure and services which makes the area attractive to people.

The major indicators of population growth in the area were observed to be urbanization and natural birth increase. For instance, residents of the study area have access to good and improved health facilities, water, roads and other facilities that make living meaningful. These facilities in turn attract people living in close proximity to the main urban areas. Being a peri-urban area, residential land use dominates and residents mostly commute to the adjoining urban areas for their businesses in order to earn a living. Other indicators of population growth in the area is the affordable rate of housing and land availability for housing development as against the adjoining urban areas where land is very expensive when they are available. Population growth being a natural phenomenon has been investigated in previous works by scholars. As observed in the study, population growth is not without its implication on food security. For instance, as the population increases, the study noted a corresponding increase in food demand.

Accurate mapping of population distribution is essential for policy-making, urban planning, administration, and for disasters and risk management. In some countries, like Nigeria, population data is not collected on a regular basis and is rarely available at a high spatial resolution. The official last census in the Federal Republic of Nigeria dates back to 2006. There is hence a strong need for a reliable, up-to-date estimate of the population number and its distribution in Nkwelle Ezunaka and Ogbunike to be able to understand the dynamism of peri-urban development in the study area. Based on the observation, it is suggested that there is need to ensure that urbanization and population growth in the study area is controlled. This is due to the fact that the population in the area is growing intensively without attendant increase in land provision because land is fixed in supply. To this end, there is need to ensure that population is

controlled probably through organizing sensitization on the need to ensure family planning as well as decentralization of facilities and infrastructure in adjoining rural areas.

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